

AUTUMN CRUISE, 2024

Aim: Collect field data to improve WP1's model parameterization & predictive potential related to the seasonal vertical migration, lipids and diapause of *Calanus*.

Ship: R/V Helmer Hanssen

Departure: 12th October, early morning from Tromsø

Arrival: 14th June, evening in Tromsø

Study area: Malangsdjupet (Troms)

Strategy: Due to this being a short cruise, classic shipboard sampling is only planned. There will be no deployment of autonomous vehicles. The sampling strategy includes:

1. Deployment of plankton nets in selected stations (WP2 net) – samples will be processed at UiT and become a part of a masters project led by Sünnje.
2. CTD + Fluorescence profiles (shipboard CTDF)
3. Water samples for the analyses of chlorophyll (only a few stations, as the phytoplankton bloom should be over by now)
4. Acoustics transect from shelf to shelfbreak (perhaps a bit offshore, depending on the available time)
5. There will be NO trawling for fish or microzooplankton

